

Report on the digital accessibility assessment

- **For some people internet is difficult to use. This often has to do with the technology (access to computer):**
 - For example **blind people** CANNOT see the screen, they CANNOT see the pictures and texts of a website. But they can hear. That's why blind people use a special program to navigate a website that reads the information other people see. This program is called screen reader. But the screen reader only reads information which is inserted in the right way.
 - Or for example **people with motor disabilities**, they CANNOT use the mouse properly. That's why it is important that every website can be used also with the keyboard.
- **Other people have difficulties with the content of websites. Content means with the texts, photos or videos:**
 - The content can be complicated or confusing for people with cognitive disabilities. It is important that the information is clear, structured and the language is easy to read.

The SuCoLo project wants to be inclusive for all. That means that everyone should be able to get in contact with the project. We want everyone to find all the information about the project on the SuCoLo website and on the MOQO App, when they want to rent cargo bikes in Merano.

What are the main aspects of digital accessibility?

Perceptibility: The structure and menu of the website need to be very clear. The text should be short and easy to read. The contrast between text and background needs to be strong. The content has to be made for screen reader. Videos and pictures must have an alternative text description. Subtitles or videos in sign language are better. Videos should never start on their own.

Usability: A website should be navigable by mouse and computer keyboard.

Comprehensibility: The content of the website must be simple and easy to understand.

Robustness: A website should work on all computers or other devices. Devices means mobile phones or tablets. Important are also accessible PDF documents.

We made a digital accessibility test of the SuCoLo website in 4 steps:

1. **Testing with software programs:** there are specific programs to test websites. These programs show what is wrong. For example, the used colors for text and background in a website do NOT have enough contrast. Or the titles of the sections in the website are wrong. Or pictures do NOT have text descriptions for blind people.
2. **Testing with a group of people with and without disabilities:** people use internet in a very different way. It is important to test the usability of a website for all the different needs of people. We tested the usability of our website asking different people if or where they have problems using our website. Therefore we used a questionnaire for our testing group.

3. **Collection of the result:** all the problems we found testing and using the SuCoLo website have been described in a document. Then the testing team made suggestions on how the SuCoLo website could be improved making it more accessible.
4. **Deliverable:** this final document has been given to the responsible partner and published on the website. Now we know the problems and can make our website better.

After the test, digital accessibility can be improved

When we tested the SuCoLo website and the app MOQO, we found a few things that need to be improved. We have communicated the things that need to be improved to the responsible project partner.

Things can now be corrected. This makes the website accessible for everyone.

And we have suggested adding a notification option so that anyone can write to us in order to signal problems regarding digital accessibility.

Proposal for better accessibility of content:

The SuCoLo project has a complex structure and so has the homepage.

To make the content accessible for everyone a graphical proposal of a landing page in Easy-to-read-Language was made.

Figure: Graphical proposal homepage www.sucolo.eu with Easy-to-read-language

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